

EM-TECH - Innovative e-motor technologies covering e-axles and e-corners vehicle architectures for high-efficient and sustainable e-mobility

EM-TECH

Objectives

EM-TECH brings together 10 participants from industry and academia to develop novel solutions to push the boundaries of electric machine technology for automotive traction, through:

- i) innovative direct and active cooling designs;
- ii) virtual sensing functionalities for the high-fidelity real-time estimation of the operating condition of the machine;
- iii) enhanced machine control, bringing reduced design and operating conservativeness enabled by ii);
- iv) electric gearing to provide enhanced operational flexibility and energy efficiency;

v) digital twin based optimisation, embedding systematic consideration of Life Cycle Analysis and Life Cycle Costing aspects since the early design stages; and
vi) adoption of recycled permanent magnets and circularity solutions.

EM-TECH obtained the support of several car makers (AUDI AG and Changan UK R&D Centre Ltd) as well as a Tier 1 supplier (PUNCH Turino S.p.A.), which will strengthen the exploitation strategy.

We are very much looking forward to the cooperation.

Facts

Funding scheme: HORIZON-CL5-2022-D5-01-09

Status: Project start by January 1st, 2023

Duration: 3 years

Consortium: 10 partners

Total budget: approx. 4.920 k€

Coordinator: AVL List GmbH

EM-TECH Partners

The EM-TECH consortium partners are:

1. AVL List GmbH
2. Technical University of Ilmenau
3. Politecnico di Torino
4. Elaphe Pogonske Tehnologije Doo
5. Traxial BV
6. Ideas & Motion SRL
7. METTOP GmbH (UrbanGold)
8. Armengaud Innovate GmbH
9. University of Surrey
10. University of Bath

EM-TECH overall approach

The proposed innovations will be implemented in new series of radial flux direct drive in-wheel motors characterised by so far unexplored levels of torque density ($>150 \text{ Nm/litre}$, $>50 \text{ Nm/kg}$), and on-board single stator double rotor type ironless axial flux machines providing power density and specific power levels in excess of 30 kW/litre and 10 kW/kg . The solutions will address both passenger car and van applications

(continuous power levels of $50 \text{ kW} - 120 \text{ kW}$), providing competitive costs ($<6 \text{ Euro/kg}$ for a production of $100000 \text{ units/year}$), and leading to significant reduction of motor energy loss during real vehicle operation ($>25\%$), and to $>60\%$ decrease of the rare earth content, including implementation of magnet recycling solutions.

